

Formal Onboarding of doctoral candidates - Lessons Learned from Non-academic Partners

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Maximum length: 1000 words

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Purpose

Onboarding is a process of integrating new employees into the organisation, thereby enhancing both professional, social, cultural and organisational integration. As a result, employees feel welcomed as part of the organisation and better prepared for the tasks awaiting them. The sooner the new employee feels welcome and fully informed, the better and quicker they will be able to contribute to the organisation successfully. Onboarding procedures are common in the private sector but often absent in academic institutions. In particular for newly hired Early Career Researchers (ESR), namely PhD candidates, such procedures will strongly impact both their integration into the organisation and clarification of roles and responsibilities of all stakeholders involved in their programme. In order to maximize their impact, it is therefore important that onboarding procedures are approved and supported by supervisors and Postgraduate offices. While it has been shown that successful onboarding contributes to

increased well-being and motivation, many ESRs often feel somewhat lost and poorly supported when entering academia, leading to doubt, insecurity and sometimes even an early abandonment of their research project. There are a very well-developed onboarding processes for the general and administrative staff at a number of European and American universities, or it is at least they are starting to be established. The checklists and toolboxes that can be found online (e.g. Harvard), show that these processes can be compared to the private sector. The knowledge of successful onboarding processes is therefore already established in these universities. However, for Postdocs and PhD candidates, who are in temporary employment, such a process is only provided for in exceptional cases and often does not go beyond an orientation day. The fact that this can impact not only on the performance and motivation, but also on the mental health of PhD candidates, seems obvious but has not yet been studied in depth.

Lessons learnt from the academic partners involved with our project correspond with the current needs in academia to establish a structural procedure consisting of regular meetings of a PhD candidate and their supervisor helping to clarify the expectations, obtaining feedback from both sides and improving the atmosphere the PhD candidate works and studies in.

Design

Within the Pride-network, we established an onboarding working group who's aims are to: : i) define current trends in private sector onboarding, ii) define onboarding guidelines based on the best practices, taking into account the differences between the academic environment and the private sector, and subsequently iii) implement and pilot our suggested guidelines/onboarding program. The underlying methodology consists of literature review and interviews with both PhD candidates as well as HR managers with prior experience in the private sector (Czech Republic). Based on this data we then propose an onboarding programme that will be piloted from autumn 2023 onwards.

Results

Crucial concepts during this procedure outcomes we achieved through interviews with PhD candidates who work/worked in a private sector. They are: i) feeling of belonging to the organisation, ii) feeling of comfort and ongoing support and lastly iii) not being afraid to raise any questions during the first months of transition. At the ReMO conference, we would like to present the analysis and results as they form the foundation to build onboarding procedures

within our institutions. We encourage an active discussion with the audience as to how onboarding procedure could take shape in their context and which obstacles we should overcome. Suggestions and best practice from non-academic sector, such as Job description and Adaptation plan, will be presented. These actions help to reassure the newly hired employee during the first steps of onboarding. Furthermore, a set of model questions that are used during assessment interviews will be shared to manifest what works in non-academic sector. The onboarding procedure responds to the mental health strategy in the Czech university environment with one of its goals being to implement this procedure right from the start of the PhD studies. If onboarding works well from the beginning and the new PhD candidate feels enough support both from their supervisor and from the PhD support service office, it can reduce the initial stress level that many newcomers experience.

Implications

Based on our work so far, we recommend to:

- Make onboarding a current part of the Czech university system;
- Focus on mental health of a PhD candidate and feeling of belonging into the organisation;
- Clarify the expectations of both the Student and the Principal Supervisor.
- Create and implement an agreed adaptation plan strategy;
- Use milestones, such as 1 day, 30, 90, 180 days and a year to check the PhD's adaptation success;
- Suggest improvements and to implement them.

Acknowledgments

Resources

- (1) Bauer, T. N. (2010). Onboarding new employees: Maximizing Success. *SHRM Foundation's Effective Practice Guidelines Series*.
- (2) "This article is based upon work from the ReMO COST Action on Researcher Mental Health, CA19117, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology)."